

THE CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE MEMBERSHIP OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION

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***Abstract:** In the article, the advantages and disadvantages that might arise after joining Uzbekistan to the World Trade Organization are discussed by the author. In addition, recommendations and suggestions are put forward by analyzing other experiences of the member-states to prevent and simplify the process and participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

***Key words:** diplomatic missions, WTO Secretariat, trilateral, dialogue, multilateral trading system, necessary documents, accession, non-discrimination, privileges, preferential treatment, national basis, importation, anti-dumping measures, unfair competition, freedom of the market, transactions.*

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КРИТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЧЛЕНСТВА УЗБЕКИСТАНА ВО ВСЕМИРНОЙ ТОРОВОЙ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ

***Аннотация;** В статье автором обсуждаются преимущества и недостатки, которые могут возникнуть после вступления Узбекистана во Всемирную торговую организацию. Кроме того, на основе анализа другого*

опыта государств-членов выдвигаются рекомендации и предложения по предотвращению и упрощению процесса и участия Республики Узбекистан.

Ключевые слова: *дипломатические представительства, Секретариат ВТО, трехсторонний, диалог, многосторонняя торговая система, необходимые документы, присоединение, не-дискриминация, привилегии, преференциальный режим, национальная основа, импорт, антидемпинговые меры, недобросовестная конкуренция, свобода рынка, сделки.*

Foreword

As a part of the process regarding Uzbekistan's accession towards the World Trade Organization (referred to hereinafter as WTO), Tashkent convened a coordination meeting with donor nations and pertinent international organizations. At the event, more than 50 participating diplomatic missions from prestigious and well-recognized organizations such as the WTO Secretariat, the German Society for International Cooperation (GIZ), the Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency (TIKA), the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), in their turn, had contributed to increasing its significance at a worldwide scale. By the end of the conference, the head of the cooperation department of the European Union (hereinafter EU) delegation in Uzbekistan, François Bejo, hinted in her speech at the readiness of the EU to offer unwavering support in this area. It is worth noting that it was not big news as this choice of action by the EU was expected ab initio, given the purpose of the meeting.

According to information reported by the press called Kun.uz, a trilateral dialogue had been held at the Ministry of Investment via videoconference between Deputy Minister Badriddin Obidov and the Chairman of the working

group of Uzbekistan on WTO membership, Korean Ambassador to Geneva Lee Teho and Director of WTO Secretariat Membership Department Maika Osikawa. Likewise, there was a statement concerning the fact that Uzbekistan had handed over to the WTO secretariat and their member countries all the necessary documents for the 6th meeting of the working group. Besides, Mark Linscott, appointed advisor on Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO, and Jason Gilpin appointed Director of the U.S. Mission for International Development (USAID), in negotiations with Ambassador of Uzbekistan Javlon Vakhobov, said that the United States will help Uzbekistan on its way to WTO membership.

To put all the above-mentioned another way, their meaning is that the following phase in entering the WTO was brought in for Uzbekistan. It seems unavoidable that the State will become one of them, respectful of when exactly will it be. Under these circumstances, the time to look through the pros and cons of being a true member of this institution has arrived.

Main body; privileges:

It would be a sensible and relevant way to proceed to the main part of the article by exploring the privileges of membership in such an international platform, i.e., let's jump right into it.

First and foremost, it should be mentioned that the WTO, since its establishment, created a multilateral trading system that is covered by a wide range of agreements regulating multiple activities related to trade directly. That is, imagine there is room for those who want to feel secure when it comes to trade relationships with persons or entities throughout the world. Bearing in mind that every single country has a propensity for taking all credit in any legal relationships they are involved in if possible without considering the interest of

others, it makes reasonable sense for the existence of the WTO. Thus, WTO intends to make an environment and a system that allows the interests of members to be taken into account as fairly as possible. In consideration of it, becoming a true part means to give what is given to you in each separate case for Uzbekistan. There are no words to describe exactly the positive effects of it if world-trade ruling countries such as in the USA, China, Canada, Germany, England, Italy, and France are put to that table.

Walking through the benefits that WTO put forward, it is impossible to overlook NT and MFN. They together incorporate the non-discrimination obligation set out under the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade signed on 30 October 30, 1947. MFN, aka most-favored-nation treatment, is whether a country favors products, services, or service suppliers from some countries over like products, services, or service suppliers from other countries. It prohibits a country from discrimination between and among other countries. A national treatment (NT) is whether a country favors itself over other countries, that is, to prohibit a country from discriminating against other countries¹. In simple terms, the former obligation relates to a condition where the government's privileges and preferential treatment are to be applied to all foreign goods and services in the like circumstances, and for the forming equal treatment upon the nationals and foreign ones is attributed to the latter.

In all fairness, it had better be noted that both treatments have special circumstances which provide a reasonable ground to step aside, nevertheless, there is no need to refer to them right now. Assuming Uzbekistan enters into the WTO, it obliges itself to treat in a similar way to all foreign investors, goods, and services, and, by doing so the State will be in that mentioned cozy environment within external territories, whether where the market is placed as

¹ Van den Bossche, P. (2005). *The Law and Policy of the World Trade Organization*. Fifth ed. Cambridge University Press, United Kingdom.

long as the area of land belongs to one of members. This is to say, the investors from Uzbekistan and goods and services designed within its land will be put in a similar environment with gigantic countries, in its all means, such as the USA, China, France, and Germany in foreign markets. There is no way to compete with the above-mentioned or such countries in terms of trade in the phase in which the State is walking currently. Hence, MFN will indeed be beneficial to the State in particular. As to the NT rule, the situation is the same, that is, everything out of the State will be treated equally with the nationals of the host country if the State imposes this obligation within its territory first. Taking into account the aforementioned grounds, it can be said that becoming a part of the WTO guarantees a strong shield against discrimination in trade and services internationally which is ipso facto crucial to that domain.

What is more, NT and MFN rules provide an opportunity for foreign investors to feel secure while in the State. That is, the flow of investment will change to a good trajectory. To apply those rules, a national basis will be required and, therefore, the Uzbek Law will be improved and, more importantly, will be stabilized.

Besides, as far as importing is concerned, there is no way but to think about specific demands outlined by every host country. Broadly speaking, they are called as barriers in a trade law. In the WTO platform, there are tariff and non-tariff barriers to market access. The first includes customs duties which might be a cornerstone of import operations. As for the latter, the quantitative restrictions, namely quotas, customs formalities, technical barriers to trade, unfair and arbitrary application of trade regulation, sanitary and phytosanitary measures, lack of transparency of trade regulation, and government procurement practices are considered.

All of them together form parts of the key to opening a destined market. As noted above, customs duties are a sort of payment imposed by the

government upon every importing goods. In the case of China – Auto Parts (2009), the Panel of WTO held that for a charge to constitute a customs duty, the obligation to pay it must accrue at the moment and by virtue of or on importation².

Let's see that in terms of Uzbekistan. It is no secret that the automobile market of the State is currently in a poor condition since there is no other option but the cars offered by the national company UzAuto Motors (hereinafter the company). That is due to the customs duties applied to foreign cars by the government in favor of this company. In other words, the cost is based on the features of the very imported car. To be more specific, according to the Uzbek legislation, the charge for importing is the amount of 30 %, the Value Added Tax is 15 % right now, the road charge of 2.5%, and charges related to impacting on the environment. That is about 60 % out of the cost value of the car. Take, for example, you want to drive the BMW 8 (price 147,500 US dollars) on the road of Uzbekistan, and in order to do so you are obliged to pay a customs duty in the amount of 236,000 US dollars. For this very reason, on the roadways of Uzbekistan there are few cars made out of its territory, and year by year the quality of cars manufactured by the company is declining. The price of its cars within the territory is by far higher in contrast to their price established in foreign markets, that is, a dumping policy.

After taking part in the WTO, the State has to set an equal percentage of customs duty for all foreign automobiles, whereas the company is doomed to face up to anti-dumping measures in external lands. Under these conditions, it will start to make an effort to be able to provide cars that are to be considered suitable to world standards thereof, and will, not out of its will, equalize the price in both directions. Not minor of, but the major of population of the State

² Appellate Body Reports, China – Auto Parts (2009), para. 158. With regard to the difference between a “customs duty” and “other duties and charges on imports”, Section 3.1 and fin. 212.

will enjoy cars manufactured beyond the national territory at last. So to put it another way, the outcomes of being a member are advantageous for the sake of the State in the above-stated aspect of trade.

The next thing that comes up to mind is that the quality of products in domestic markets has a chance to increase. As of today, the situation in the market seems unbalanced, since the lack of sufficient foreign segments resulted in some manufacturers taking over that branch of supplement and dictating the conditions thereof. Owing to the obligation that will be applied to every single member of WTO regarding market access, in doing so that producers will confront an unprecedented competition they never saw until now. That helps, in turn, to open the market to consumers at substantial good terms, and the product and services will be changed in the right way as it has to be. The monopolies, inter alia, in the service of the airplane, the goods of home appliances, and so on will be cracked for the interest of the populace.

By carrying out its obligations comply with the rules of the WTO the more markets will be unlocked, as the State did that for other members. This is because of the demand requiring from countries to make their markets available for the members.

Main body; not-good impacts:

Hitherto was briefly discussed the white sides of entering into the WTO. What about the other one of it? As a general rule of everything in the world, there can be nothing without the two separate parts. Thereby, in the paragraphs that follow, there will be outlined demerits thereof.

Uzbekistan's membership in the WTO will lead to a reduction in customs duties to 8-10 percent since according to the principle of market access,

previously mentioned above, the rules of tariff barriers obligate every single member-country of it to do so. Unavoidably, the state budget will suffer from this.

Secondly, prior to this event, there are works that have to be done in terms of the liberalization of the economy, the privatization of industry, and restriction of state interference in the freedom of the market. To be specific, the phase of Uzbekistan regarding the economy and the legislation right now is not stable and, to be honest, is in its infancy. Some newborn producers are to be provided with the special treatment of the State, in the beginning, to set off a long way through privileges such as subsidies. The movement of the WTO in this regard is severe, in other words, is in favor of, only if it complies with exceptions pointed out in the relevant agreements. Thus, interfering in the market to act so turns the status of the State, in most cases, into the one that broke the pivotal rules of the WTO.

Moreover, there is a huge possibility that production within the republic will be paralyzed. For example, Uzbek farmers specializing in the production of cotton products may run out of business, unable to compete with trading companies in China, India, the UAE, producing cheap and high-quality products. As a result, the crisis in agriculture worsens, thousands of hectares of land remain empty, the production of products for farmers, melon growers becomes a loss-making industry, which leads to the sale of cheap and high-quality products produced in developed countries. This creates additional problems for the State, where 70 percent of the population lives in rural areas.

Dynamics of GDP per capita in 2010-2019 developed unevenly, in 2017 this amounted to 1,491 US dollars³, which, as a result of Uzbekistan's accession

³ Omonov, Bakhtiyor, "Jahon Savdo Tashkilotiga A'zolik O'zbekistonga Nima Beradi?" *Pravachloveka.uz*, 26 Aug. 2020, pravechoveka.uz/oz/news/jahon-savdo-tashkilotiga-azolik-ozbekistonga-nima-beradi. Accessed 15 Nov. 2022.

to the WTO, as in China, may lead to an increase in unemployment and deterioration of the state of machine.

Speaking on behalf of professor Bakhtiyor Omonov, in particular, the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (Paris Document of July 24, 1971), in accordance with the law on copyright and Related Rights, prohibits the illegal reproduction of works created by national and foreign authors

– the use of unlicensed (pirated) products, the distribution of counterfeit products on CD, DVD, VCD, VHS, cases when a counterfeit copy copied to MP3 discs is freely sold on the markets and makes a profit are common throughout the State. Unfortunately, a number of tasks related to the agreement on intellectual property rights in the field of trade (TRIPS), the creation of a fair competitive environment for ideas and inventions, as well as obligations on unfair competition have not yet been solved.

It is said that one of these not-good impacts is that the unpreparedness of the State's large industries for this economic process is characterized by the fact that the prices of the domestic market for the products they produce are higher than the prices of the external market. A simple example: in July 2020, the Antimonopoly Committee considered the deputy's request for violation of the requirements of the competition law on JSC UzAuto Motors⁴. Investigations conducted by a special commission of the committee confirmed that the company unreasonably inflated the prices of cars. According to them, the prices of cars were unreasonably inflated from 3 to 19 million sums. A similar situation can be seen in the prices of the products of dozens of joint-stock companies, such as Artel, Akfa, and signature, whose monopolies are more often talked about.

⁴ “Monopoliyaga Qarshi Kurash Qo‘mitasi Raisiga “UzAuto Motors” Monopoliyasiga Oid Deputatlik So‘rovi Yuborildi.” *Kun.uz*, 29 July 2020, kun.uz/uz/news/2020/07/29/monopoliyaga-qarshi-kurashish-qomitasi-raisinga-deputatlik-sorovi-yuborildi. Accessed 15 Nov. 2022.

Main body; examples:

As located next to Uzbekistan, it will be logical to turn inside out the consequences thereof, which had been until now, for Kazakhstan. In an interview with Strategy2050.kz news agency, Kazakh Vice Minister of Trade and Integration Zhanel Kushukov stated the following.

Kazakhstan has improved the customs regulation and administration as well as the balances of the interests of the entrepreneurs and the interests of the State since joining the WTO. There has been the transition from the paper based to the electronic customs administration. The human factor is no longer plays a pivotal role when making decisions thanks to information systems, release of products is faster. In early 2019, the Single window for export and import transactions has been in place, allowing participants of foreign trade activities to receive and provide all necessary papers to run export or import transactions in one place thus saving those time and financial expenses and improving terms of trade on the whole⁵.

That is, it can be seen from the speech that the outcome of the WTO accession for Kazakhstan is currently positive. In respect of Tajikistan, for a number of reasons, the same cannot stand as has so far not substantially benefited from it in terms of trade flows.

Kyrgyzstan is now a WTO member, its trade with its neighbors will be subject to WTO rules, and the country will benefit from protection for the weaker partner when its larger neighbors join the WTO. This occurred when China joined the WTO in 2001. As more Central Asian countries join the rule-based system, the network benefits will grow⁶.

⁵ Seilkhanov, Adlet. "Kazakhstan in WTO: What Changes Have Taken Place in 4 Years." *Strategy2050.Kz*, strategy2050.kz/en/news/53723/. Accessed 15 Nov. 2022.

⁶ USPECA Project Working Group on Trade; Second Session, Berlin, 12 November 2007; USPECA/PWG-Trade/2007/EN/6

Conclusion

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WTO regulations and cooperation aided in avoiding a major trade war, which was pivotal during the global recession of 2008/09. Researchers could compare this to the 1930s, when trade wars erupted, resulting in a drop in global trade. The average tariff in the 1930s was 50%, according to (Bagwell and Staiger 2002). In the 2000s, the average tariff was 9%⁷. According to Ralph Ossa, the value of WTO in preventing trade wars could be estimated at up to \$340 billion per year⁸.

⁷ Available from: <https://econ.economicshelp.org/2007/06/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-wto.html>

⁸ Available from: <https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/wto-success-no-trade-agreement-no-trade-war>

World exports as a percentage of GDP have accelerated from 22% in 1995 (when the WTO was formed) to just under 30% in 2015, indicating the importance of trade to the world economy.

Taking everything into account, the accession of WTO will indeed have an enormous impact on all aspects of the trade, as in the present phase of development Uzbekistan will be better off with conditions set out by this institution.

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